

THE IMPORTANCE OF INDEPENDENT EDUCATION IN THE STUDY OF FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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Abstract:

In modern conditions of economic life, the employee is presented with quite serious requirements in the labor market. A specialist needs not only to have a certain set of necessary knowledge but also to be able to independently solve the professional and social tasks facing him. This article highlights the importance of independent education in the study of foreign languages in modern education.

Key words: foreign language, modern education, independent work, independent thinking, quality of lesson, effectiveness.

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However, until now, in foreign language lessons, students often passively perceive information, poorly assimilating it and practically not using it in a situation of real communication. This is due, in our opinion, to the fact that very little time is given to independent work in university curricula, without which it is impossible to fully assimilate the material. In addition, both teachers and students still face the problem of insufficient technical equipment of classrooms, i.e. Students can use the Internet, multimedia tools and educational computer programs only while doing homework, which reduces the level of teacher control. This leads to poor assimilation of language material in students with low motivation. In addition, it also affects the mood during classroom classes: unmotivated students still remain passive consumers of knowledge, unable to work creatively and independently.

Independent learning is put at the forefront of modern education today. Independent work is one of the main factors in the implementation of the ideas of the competence approach [1]. The teacher is no longer considered by the student as the only source of information, since modern young people are used to finding the information, they need on the Internet. The role of the teacher is changing at the same time, he must now be able to direct the student's work in the right direction when searching for the necessary information and processing information resources. He should teach the modern student to understand and realize responsibility for the results of his education, the importance of independent work for the most successful and effective socialization in the information society. In this regard, the author believes that the main goals of higher and vocational education are:

- preparation of a person for problem-searching activity, as a result of which independent thinking, professional mobility, the need to improve existing knowledge, as well as to acquire new ones are formed;
- improving the efficiency and effectiveness of the educational process.

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Independent work is defined by us as a variety of types of educational, practical and research tasks performed under the guidance of a teacher, in order to acquire knowledge and acquire a certain set of skills and abilities together with the experience of creative activity. Independent work is a necessary tool used when learning a foreign language. The problem of organizing independent work, which has always interested researchers in the field of pedagogy and methodology, is becoming more and more relevant today. Currently, not only the forms of independent work themselves are changing, but also the possibilities of monitoring and monitoring this process [2]. In addition, in the didactics of higher education, the essence of independent work of students has not yet been disclosed. The concept of "independent work of students" seems to be multidimensional. There are such aspects as psychological, physiological, organizational, didactic aspects that are interrelated with each other, therefore it is impossible to reveal the content of this concept by adhering to only one aspect and not considering the others.

In pedagogy, the concepts of "independent activity" and "independent work" are distinguished. They are not identical, but correlated. Independent work contributes to the development of creative independence of students. Independent work should be considered not as a form of organization of educational knowledge or a method of teaching, but rather as a means of involving students in independent cognitive activity [3].

Skillful organization of independent work has undoubted psychological and pedagogical advantages in the successful assimilation of knowledge.

The words "independence" and "independent" characterize the special quality of the work performed by a person and a certain quality of personality. The second includes consciousness, motivation of actions, manifestation of will, which is based on an understanding of the need to act in these circumstances in accordance with one's inner position and one's own decision, not subject to other people's influences and suggestions [4].

Independent work in a broad sense can be understood as the totality of the student's independent activity. This can be both work in the classroom and outside it. At the same time, the teacher can either perform certain roles in the organization of independent work, or not.

Independence in learning is a necessary condition for the activation of cognitive processes and the entire educational activity of the student, being one of the ways to form the necessary competencies to prepare future specialists for life and work in the rapidly changing conditions of the modern world, rapidly developing scientific knowledge and constantly updated technology.

The student cannot remain neutral and passive at the same time. Very often, inhibition may occur in the student's perception due to the teacher's hypertrophied explanations. Despite repeated explanations of the material by the teacher, the effect of such explanations can be very low, since students may have the impression that this material is familiar to them, and they have already mastered this or that skill. They remain internally passive, which means they simply do not perceive the material being studied. When explaining new material, it is not always advisable for the teacher to fully disclose the answer to the question himself. In some cases, the benefits for learning will be greater if students find the answer to this question themselves. However, for the success of the case, attention should be paid to the preliminary training of students, which provides the opportunity to independently solve the task assigned to them.

If earlier the inclusion of independent work in the educational process pursued, first of all, the goal of activating the student's work and ensuring that they acquire more solid knowledge, today it is necessary to pay so much attention to independent work also because the graduate, in order to keep up with life, will have to continuously replenish and update the baggage of competencies that he acquired while studying at a higher educational institution, solving new tasks that arise before it. The role of the leading subject in independent work belongs to the student, not to the teacher, who fully corresponds to I.A. Zimnaya's concept of independent work. According to this concept, independent work includes flexible, indirect management, carried out by both the teacher and the action program, as well as the content of the educational material, which, in turn, should contribute to the development of self-control and self-esteem. In his work I.A. Zimnaya uses the term "subject self-regulation": "Self-regulation of a student presupposes the ability to program independent activity, i.e., in relation to the conditions of the corresponding goal of activity, to choose the method of transformation of given conditions, the selection of means for this transformation, the determination of the sequence of individual actions" [5]. An important manifestation of self-regulation is also the ability to evaluate the final and intermediate results of their actions. Thus, in order to develop self-regulation, students should have the skills of goal-setting and goal-keeping, modeling their own activities, which is implemented within the framework of the formation of educational competence. This fact once again emphasizes the relationship between academic competence and independent work. The formation of academic competence directly precedes the independent work of students, since its implementation requires the possession of certain skills and abilities.

Thus, from all of the above, we can conclude that the ability and readiness for independent work must be purposefully formed with the help of organized educational activities during classroom classes. Students should have a clear understanding of the goals and objectives of learning, the sequence of educational actions when performing tasks, the purpose of each task and its significance for the formation of a particular skill or competence. To achieve this goal, the teacher should help students master not only individual rules and strategies, but a well-structured system that includes a vision of goals and ways to achieve them, a planning strategy and organization of work with selected material, control criteria and evaluation of their own results. The ability and readiness for independent activity are emerging properties of the psyche of students, and they can be formed only in conditions of transferring methods of solving simple problems to solving more complex ones [6]. In didactics, three levels of readiness for independent work are distinguished, namely: reproducing, semi-creative and creative, demonstrating the degree of formation of educational competence and the constant transition from external motivation to internal.

The advantages of independent work of students include the fact that it, causing the activity of the student, also has an individualized character. Students use information sources depending on their own needs and capabilities. Independent work has a flexible adaptive nature. This increases the responsibility of each student and, as a result, his academic performance. In the process of independent work, the student acts as an active creative person who shows erudition, creates his own worldview and culture, shows his readiness for the future profession [7].

Undoubtedly, oral speech and, first of all, speaking are carried out directly in the presence of interlocutors, whose role in the classroom is performed by the teacher and other students. However, as you know, learning to speak involves certain preparatory stages that guarantee communication, for which independent work is the most adequate form. According to our observations, a significant part of first-year students study below their capabilities precisely because of the lack of independent activity skills. In this situation, the following is required from a high school teacher:

- to help students organize their educational and cognitive activities in the most effective way;
- rationally plan and promote the implementation of independent work of students both in the classroom and outside it;
- to ensure the formation of students' general skills and skills of independent activity.

In our opinion, in order to successfully fulfill these requirements, it is necessary, first of all, to properly organize independent work, i.e. to determine its specific goals, the form in which it should be performed (oral, written or practical), choose a way to verify the results of work. In addition, a prerequisite is the obligation of work for all students. Another important condition is the control over the performance of independent work on the part of the teacher, on the one hand, and self-control of students, on the other hand. The author suggests the following correlation of methods of control and self-control with types of independent activity. The teacher controls the preparation of students for practical classes and control works during preliminary consultations and by developing test tasks. Students monitor or check their level of preparation on the oral survey itself or during written testing. If students perform a task to search, for example, for country-specific information in a foreign language to compile a report on a given topic, the teacher provides a list of recommended literature, and also voices the requirements for future work in advance. Self-control in this situation will be carried out both in the process of preparation and during the verification of the results of independent work, i.e. during an oral communication or a written presentation [8]. As for students performing creative works in a foreign language, for example, preparing a message in the power point mode with an independent choice of topic, the only form of teaching control in this case is an individual consultation. Self-control of students is again carried out in the process of preparing a message. All of the above suggests to us that during the preparation of an independent task, students inevitably awaken the desire to approach the process creatively, since creativity is one of the conditions for successful work.

Previously, most often only homework was independent. Later, independent work began to be given at the stage of consolidating knowledge and controlling their assimilation. Then she took her rightful place at the stage of familiarization with the new material, its independent comprehension. Recently, in the era of digitalization and transformation of knowledge, independent work is important at all stages of learning a foreign language.

In independent work, it is advisable to include separate links of work on language material – acquaintance with it and partially training in its use. The sources of information that students can use in the course of independent work include, first of all, as before, a textbook. An important source of information for independent work are the texts of the textbook, as well as additional texts included by the teacher in the educational process. A great role in independent

work on language material and various lexical and grammatical exercises presented in textbooks [9].

It should be noted that independent work is only relatively independent in educational conditions. Students experience the indirect influence of the teacher, who, firstly, contributes to the motivation of independent work, and secondly, ensures its rational and effective course. The more voluntary the independent work is, the more successful it is. The teacher needs to create only the grounds for the emergence of students' need for it. It makes sense to create a situation in which students would feel a shortage of learned material for communication. At the same time, they should be pointed to a specific source of information to fill this deficit.

The potential applicability in practice of the results of the work performed in the field of the chosen professional activity can contribute to the development of the creative potential of students in the process of independent work in a foreign language. This allows the student to realize himself as a future specialist in an educational situation. Such active forms of learning as multimedia presentations, games, cases, projects stimulate the student to creative activity. It is very important to have a research component in the student's independent activity, namely, preparation for scientific and practical conferences and seminars in a foreign language and participation in them, contests of research papers in a language, etc. Solving specific educational tasks through independent work contributes to the disclosure of the student's personality as a future professional. Each form of independent work has a certain degree of influence on the disclosure of the student's creative potential.

Innovations in the field of science, technology and technology, developing at a cosmic speed, are in international languages. The use of modern technical equipment in various fields of human activity requires specialists to have a good knowledge of foreign languages. For the full and proper use of the capabilities of modern technical equipment, it is necessary that the specialist knows the language of operation of this equipment well.

In the educational process, active (student-teacher interaction) and interactive (student-teacher interaction as well as with other students) forms of independent work are used. The active forms include individual classes, consultations on the topics under study, taking notes of materials on the topic under study, tests and tests, preparation of reports, etc. Interactive ones include preparation and presentation of presentations, presentations at conferences, participation in competitions and Olympiads in a foreign language, project tasks, case analysis, etc.

Control over the independent work of students is carried out in various forms: orally (reading, communication, conversation, explanation, etc.), in writing (essays, essays, articles and theses, written exercises, tests, control papers, etc.).

Special attention should be paid to the essay when organizing independent work of students in a foreign language, which pursues the following goals: the development of creative thinking, the ability to express their own thoughts in writing. With the help of this form of independent work, the teacher checks the student's ability to process the information received on the basis of its comparison, comparison and generalization, classification on the selected grounds, as well as the ability to give his own assessment of the phenomenon or event described in the essay, to express his attitude to it.

In conclusion, I would like to note that "the implementation of forms of independent work of students in foreign language classes, activating the creative potential of the individual, involves a personality-oriented approach". This is also due to the acquisition of new roles by the teacher as the initiator of independent educational, cognitive and communicative activities of students, such as a tutor, a teaching assistant, etc.

Thus, we can say that at the present stage, independent activity in learning a foreign language is of great importance, because, firstly, it promotes the development of a creative approach, and secondly, it strengthens the sense of personal responsibility and interest in the subject and, consequently, increases the motivation of students in the process of mastering language material. A foreign language teacher, according to the author, should move away from the previous system of presenting the subject, when teaching is mainly reduced to transmitting information about the language. It is necessary to master an interactive way of teaching, when students, getting acquainted with new material, immediately learn to use it in practice through performing independent tasks. As a result, students, instead of passively perceiving information about the language system, actually recreate it for themselves anew. And then they can formulate the problem themselves, analyze ways to solve it and look for the right answer. Their future competitiveness in the labor market depends on how soon students learn to do this. Independent work is designed to create the necessary conditions for students to master the necessary knowledge and develop their thinking.

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